

Effective Reading Strategies for Lyceum Students

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Abstract

Recent technological advancements have transformed reading habits in significant ways, extending beyond how students engage with traditional textbooks. Unfortunately, these changes have also negatively impacted students' reading skills. With easy access to entertainment on cell phones, students often favor reading informal content over books. This preference for informal language, prevalent on social media and messaging apps, has led to a range of issues: students report less enjoyment in reading, reduced critical thinking skills, ineffective reading habits, and a lack of strategic approach—all contributing to their overall decline in motivation to read. This review explores theories and past studies regarding the influence of reading strategies on students' reading comprehension. Findings reveal that applying structured reading strategies has a positive effect on comprehension skills, demonstrating that these strategies significantly enhance students' ability to read and understand content.

Keywords: reading comprehension, language learning strategies, reading strategies in-depth reading comprehension

Introduction

In this modern era, engagement with print text or textbooks is no longer the only aspect of literacy that has changed due to current technological breakthroughs (Yang et al., 2018).

However, this advancement in technology has negatively impacted students' reading abilities. One key reason for their below-average proficiency in reading comprehension is the tendency to choose entertainment content on smartphones—such as social media messages, blogs, webtoons, and other digital media—over academic or educational reading material. While promoting the importance of being a healthy digital citizen, having students complete smaller exercises for multi-tasking between using technology and learning the lesson material will ensure students are confident and comfortable. Research recommends that having a visual reminder and posting it when students are feeling like they

can't multitask because they are distracted by technology, is a healthy way to promote staying on track (Lettrick, 2016).

Even if the research failed to demonstrate whether technology increased students' scores in reading, it has shown that technology helps students to be independent, more active, more motivated, and more collaborative (Rufaidah et al., 2021; Jaleel & Anuroofa, 2017).

One of the benefits of reading according to Suyitno (1985: 37-38) is obtaining a reduction of consciousness for the sake of reading as a means of obtaining information. Prior to technological progress, learners loved to read and receive information or material from a press. However, as technology comes with various information media, learners have a decline in interest in reading because they are distracted by technology.

Reading interest is shaped by both personal and institutional factors. On a personal level, elements such as intelligence, age, gender, reading skills, attitude, and psychological needs play a significant role. Institutional influences encompass the availability of suitable reading materials, social background, ethnic groups, and the impact of peers, family, teachers, and media sources like television and movies. These combined factors collectively influence how students engage with reading and develop their interest in it.

In language teaching contexts, prioritizing reading strategy instruction is essential, as it plays a key role in enhancing students' comprehension skills. Teaching reading strategies should be a primary focus in language classes, helping students to process texts more effectively and engage in thorough reading. When time permits, language teachers should allocate adequate classroom hours to guide students through language learning strategies, accelerating their reading comprehension development. However, if direct instruction time is limited, teachers can support students by offering supplementary materials, encouraging self-directed activities that reinforce strategic reading skills and promote independent learning.

It is in line with Sari et al. (2020) who state that compared to reading textbooks which are considered a boring activity, students found reading messages from social media applications, storybooks, and comics on a smartphone to be more fascinating. Consequently, students are not used to reading or comprehending standard words because social media and messaging applications tend to use informal language, which causes them to lack formal vocabulary (Sari et al., 2020). Not only do they lack formal vocabulary, but students also get several troubles, such as low interest in reading, low critical thinking skills, poor reading style, and lack of strategy, eventually making them lose motivation to read (Febtisari & Fitrawati, 2017).

Reading is a unique cognitive process that serves as a vital means of acquiring knowledge, distinct from methods like listening or observation. Unlike these other methods, reading often requires interpretation and active analysis, engaging the reader in making sense of the content. This interpretative aspect makes reading a critical skill for students, as it enables them not only to gather information but also to comprehend and critically evaluate it. Developing strong reading skills thus supports students in building deeper understanding and analytical abilities, essential for their academic and personal growth.

Reading is an essential skill for students, with a range of strategies available to enhance both comprehension and speed. Techniques like scanning, skimming, intensive reading, and extensive reading each serve different purposes based on the text type and the reader's goals. By understanding these diverse methods, students can better select the most effective approach for each reading task.

With regular practice, these strategies can help students build the proficiency needed for fluent, efficient reading, allowing them to tackle various texts with confidence and skill.

Reading comprehension is a vital skill for students throughout their academic journey, yet it remains a challenge for many, particularly those in secondary education who are low-achieving readers. These students often face difficulties in understanding and retaining information from their reading, which can impact their overall learning and academic success. Developing strong reading comprehension skills is therefore crucial, as it enables students not only to grasp the material but also to engage with content on a deeper level, improving their academic performance and confidence

References

1. Alimdjanovna, I. S. (2022). Linguistic features of phraseological units representing space
2. Febtisari, M., & Fitrawati. (2017). Improving Student's Reading Comprehension of Descriptive Text by Using Collaborative Strategic Reading (CSR) to Eight Grade Students at Junior High School. *Journal of English Language Teaching*, 6(1), 334–340.
3. Джалилова, Г. Х. (2023). ЛЕКСИКА КАК ФАКТОР, СПОСОБСТВУЮЩИЙ ФОРМИРОВАНИЮ ИМИДЖА ПЕЧАТНОГО ИЗДАНИЯ. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 2(18), 213-217.
4. Sultanova, S. U., & Ikramova, S. A. (2023). THE CONCEPT OF COMPETITION AND ITS MANIFESTATION IN DIGITAL JOURNALISM. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(3), 105-111.
5. Lettrick, S. (2016, May 16). The clash of brain development and classroom technology. [Web log post]. *Learning and the Brain*. <https://www.learningandthebrain.com/blog/brain-development-and-classroom-technology/>
6. Sari, M. H., Susetyo, Noermanzah, Wardhana, D. E. C., & Kusumaningsih, D. (2020). Understanding the Level of Students' Reading Comprehension Ability. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(5), 1848–1855
7. Yang, X., Kuo, L. J., Ji, X., & McTigue, E. (2018). A Critical Examination of the Relationship among Research, Theory, and Practice: Technology and Reading Instruction. *Computers and Education*, 125, 62–73.
8. Yunusova, Z. (2023). THE CHARACTERISTICS OF SCIENTIFIC DISCOURSE IN THE ESP CONTEXT. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(22), 72-74.
9. Yunusova, Z. (2024). Challenges and Prospects of Teaching English for Journalism Students. *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521)*, 2(6), 328-330.
10. Yunusova, Z. (2024). Challenges and Opportunities in Teaching English to Journalism Students. *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521)*, 2(6), 339-341.